

Gender Differences in Organizational Health and Burnout among Industrial Workers

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An organization's ability to achieve its goals through adaptive and innovative practices reflects its overall health. Organizational health functions as an internal system that emphasizes trust, culture, and effective functioning, while considering the biological, psychological, and social dimensions of human life. In industrial settings, however, burnout has emerged as a growing concern, contributing to various health-related problems among employees. Keeping these perspectives in view, the present study on Organizational health and Burnout was conducted in the industrial areas of Haryana and nearby state. The sample comprised 190 workers, including 95 males and 95 females. The study aimed to examine the relationship between employee burnout and organizational health. The data was analyzed by using Pearson Product Moment method of Correlation and t- test. The findings revealed a significant negative relationship between burnout and organizational health. Additionally, the study underscored the importance of exploring gender differences in burnout and organizational health.

Keywords: Health, organization, burnout and employees

Burnout

An intense reaction to ongoing psychic and interpersonal strain at the workplace is known as burnout, a type of psychological disease. People who engage in "people work" of any kind may experience depersonalization, diminished personal accomplishment, and emotional tiredness. Excessive and protracted job stress is the first step toward burnout. Workers who experience physical strain are more likely to be irritable, tense, and exhausted (Valsania et al., 2022). When an employee defensively handles their work and becomes indifferent, cynical, or inflexible, they experience burnout. It is a condition of mental, emotional, and bodily tiredness brought on by prolonged exposure to emotionally taxing circumstances. Burnout-causing elements include unclear responsibilities, role overload, role conflict, and role ambiguity. When an employee has role overload, they take on additional responsibilities, never back down, and continue to take on more work than they can manage until they eventually get exhausted. When an employee has competing work duties, they may feel drawn to them and attempt to complete all of the work equally well without setting priorities. This is known as role conflict. Feelings of extreme stress or tiredness may be the result (Maslach & Jackson, 1981).

Burnout Symptoms

Burnout manifests itself in several ways, including behavioral, emotional, and physical symptoms. Physical symptoms include physical exhaustion, recurrent sickness, and sleep issues (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Disillusionment with the work, a loss of purpose and cynicism toward our organizations or clients, a sense of

helplessness, frustration with our efforts and our inability to alter the course of events, intense anger toward those we hold accountable for the situation and feelings of depression and loneliness are examples of emotional symptoms. Increasing disengagement from co-workers, higher absenteeism, harsher team dynamics, a noticeable decline in our dedication to our work, and greater alcohol intake are examples of behavioural indicators (Ozturk, 2020).

Burnout Types

The primary characteristic of burnout and the most noticeable sign of this complicated condition is exhaustion. Exhaustion is the main component of burnout that has been extensively studied and reported. Some contend that the other two components of the condition are incidental or superfluous due to the significant correlation between exhaustion and burnout. Exhaustion is a necessary but insufficient requirement for burnout, though. One would completely lose sight of the issue if one were to examine burnout in isolation and concentrate only on the personal tiredness component (Shirom, 1989).

The stress component of burnout is represented by weariness, but it misses important facets of how people relate to their jobs. It is not something that is just felt; rather, it causes people to take steps to emotionally and mentally separate themselves from their work, most likely as a coping mechanism for the overwhelming amount of labour. By deliberately neglecting the characteristics that make service recipients unique and interesting individuals, depersonalization is an attempt to remove oneself from them. Their demands are easier to manage when they are perceived as impersonal objects of one's effort. People outside of the human services use cognitive distancing by adopting a cynical or apathetic perspective when they are exhausted and disheartened. Burnout research often reveals a significant association between fatigue and cynicism (depersonalization) across a range of organizational and occupational situations since distancing is such a rapid reaction to exhaustion (Maslach et al., 2001). The connection between the other two types of burnout and inefficacy (lower personal accomplishment) is a little more complicated. In certain cases, it

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seems to be partially a result of either fatigue, distrust, or both (Byrne, 1994; Lee & Ashforth, 1996). One's sense of effectiveness is likely to be undermined by a work environment with persistent, excessive demands that lead to fatigue or cynicism. Effectiveness is also hampered by depersonalization or exhaustion: It is hard to feel proud of oneself when one is worn out or when one feels apathetic toward others. On the other hand, inefficacy seems to develop concurrently rather than sequentially with the other two characteristics of burnout in different job environments. Lack of pertinent resources appears to be the more obvious cause of ineffectiveness, while social conflict and work stress lead to fatigue and cynicism (Leiter, 1993). Burnout is significant because it is linked to significant effects for both the individual and the workplace. The majority of the results that have been examined have been associated with work performance. Given that burnout is regarded as a stress condition, health outcomes have also been studied. However, due to the emphasis on self-report measures (instead of other markers of performance or health), given the comparatively small number of methodological designs that enable causal conclusions, the research findings must be evaluated cautiously (Maslach et al., 2001).

Work Performance

Burnout has been connected to several occupational withdrawal behaviors, including the intention to quit, actual turnover, and absenteeism. However, those who continue to work are less productive and effective as a result of burnout. Consequently, it is associated with decreased job satisfaction and a reduced degree of commitment to the role or the organization (Rifin & Danaee, 2023). Co-workers may suffer from burnout as a result of increased interpersonal friction and interference with work-related tasks. Burnout can therefore be "contagious" and spread through casual interactions at work. People's personal lives are negatively impacted by burnout (Wilmar et al., 2000).

Burke and Greenglass (2001) stressed that burnout is a personal experience that is unique to the workplace. Numerous studies have examined quantitative job demands and discovered that burnout is a reaction to overburden. Burnout, especially the depletion dimension, is substantially and persistently correlated with experienced workload and time constraint. Self-reports of stress as well as more objective measurements of demands (such as the number of clients & hours worked) exhibit this tendency.

Role ambiguity and conflict have been the major focus of certain studies of qualitative job demands, and they both consistently demonstrate a moderate to strong association with burnout. While role ambiguity arises when there is insufficient information to perform the job effectively, role conflict arises when competing demands at work must be fulfilled. Additional qualitative work requirements. Role ambiguity and conflict have been the main focus of certain studies of qualitative job demands, and they both consistently demonstrate a moderate to elevated correlation with burnout. While role ambiguity arises when there is insufficient information to perform the job effectively, role conflict arises when competing demands at work must be fulfilled (Wilmar et al., 2004).

Organizational Characteristics

Employee life has been significantly impacted by the numerous changes that organizations have seen, such as downsizing and mergers. This is particularly apparent when there are shifts in the

psychological contract, or the perception of what the employer must provide based on alleged pledges of reciprocal trade. Employees are now expected to provide more in terms of time, effort, skills, and flexibility, even while they receive fewer career opportunities, lifetime employment, job security, and other perks. Because it undermines the idea of reciprocity, which is essential to preserving well-being, breaking the psychological contract is likely to lead to burnout (Rousseau, 1995).

Zapf et al. (2001) concluded that burnout was more strongly associated with typical job-related stressors (such as workload, time constraints, or role conflicts) than with client-related stressors (such as challenges interacting with clients, frequent contact with patients who are chronically or terminally ill, or confrontation with death and dying). Recent research, however, has focused on work-related emotions and variables (e.g., the need to express or repress emotions at work, the need to be emotionally sympathetic) and has discovered that these factors do account for additional variance in burnout scores beyond job stressors.

The demographic characteristic most frequently associated with burnout is age, out of all those that have been investigated. Burnout is observed to be more prevalent among younger workers than among older workers. Because age is sometimes conflated with professional experience, burnout appears to be more likely to occur early in one's career. The reasoning for this interpretation has not been extensively studied. However, these results should be interpreted cautiously because of the problem of survival bias, which states that people who burn out early in their careers are likely to quit, leaving behind the survivors who later exhibit lower levels of burnout (Marchand, Blance, & Beauregard, 2018). Gender has not proven to be a significant predictor of burnout, despite some suggestions that it is more common among women. Some research indicates that women are more likely than men to experience burnout. While other studies find no general differences. Males tend to score higher on cynicism, which is the one little but continuous sex difference. Additionally, some research shows that women tend to score somewhat higher on fatigue. These results could be explained by the confounding of sex and occupation (for example, police officers are more likely to be men, while nurses are more likely to be women), but they may also be related to gender role expectations (Purvanova & Muros, 2010). When it comes to marital status, single people Men in particular appear to be more susceptible to burnout than married individuals. Burnout appears to be more common among singles than among divorced people (Canadas et al., 2018). Education is confused with other factors like occupation and status, it is unclear how to interpret this result. Higher educated individuals may work in more demanding and stressful occupation (Kabito et al., 2020).

Personal Factor

Individuals contribute special traits to the interaction rather than just reacting to the work environment. These individual aspects include work-related attitudes, long-lasting personality traits, and demographic variables. It has been discovered that a number of these distinct traits are connected to exhaustion. These correlations, however, are not as strong as those between situational conditions and burnout, indicating that burnout is more of a social than an individual phenomenon. Jenkins and Maslach (1994) concluded that individuals who had better psychological health during their In addition to having better levels of involvement and job satisfaction,

teens and young adults were more likely to begin and maintain such employment.

Organizational Health

Organizations must adapt to their surroundings to survive. It is the management's duty to raise an organization's standard of living and make it healthier. The key components of health are life, growth, and vitality, all of which can be easily altered by an organization that has a clear sense of its own purpose and identity (Daniel et al., 1978).

Miles (1973) stated that the Organizational health is made up of various secondary, relatively long-lasting system characteristics that go beyond immediate efficacy. In a way, a healthy organization not only survives in its surroundings but also manages to cope well throughout time and keeps improving and expanding its capacity for both survival and coping. Goal focus, effective communication, resource utilization, optional power equalization, cohesion, morale, innovation, autonomy, adaptation, and adequate problem-solving are all components of organizational health.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the significance of the relationship between burnout and the organizational health of industrial workers.
- To assess how significant gender-based variations are in the organizational health variable.
- To assess the significance of gender-based variations in the burnout variable.

Method

Participants

The present study's sample was chosen at random from a variety of sectors in the state of Haryana and the surrounding area. Ninety-five male and ninety-five female employees made up the research sample

size of 190 personnel. The age range was 30 to 45 years. Some demographic variables, like Age and sex, are included in the study. An attempt has been made to make the sample more meaningful, representative, and in line with the study's goals.

Measures

The Maslach Inventory of Burnout: This scale was developed by Susan, Jackson, Michael, Leiter, and Maslach in 1981. This scale has sixteen items in total, which are separated into three subscales: Professional Efficacy (PE), Cynicism (Cy), and Exhaustion (Ex). This scale's validity and reliability scores are 0.68 and 0.82, in that order.

The Organizational Health Inventory: This Inventory was developed by Taj in 1997. The 40 objects on the scale are divided into three dimensions, including 1. Dimensions of the Task (A. Goal Concentration, B. Enough Communication C. Equalization of additional Power 2. Dimensions of Maintenance Needs (D. Resource Utilization) F. Morale E. Cohesion 3. Development and adaptability dimensions (G. Creativity), H. Independence, I. Adaptation, J. Adequacy of problem-solving issues. A five-point rating system is used for this scale. This scale's validity and reliability scores are 0.85 and 0.94, respectively.

Procedure

Raw data was collected with the help of standardized questionnaires on the selected sample to achieve the objectives of the study. It was analyzed with the help of some statistical tools.

Statistical Analysis

The gathered raw data were examined using a number of statistical techniques, such as the mean, standard deviation, Pearson product-moment method of correlation, and t-test.

Results and Discussion

Table 1
Burnout and Organizational Health Correlation Coefficient

Burnout Dimensions	Variable of Organizational Health Dimensions		
	Task Conferred Dimension	Maintenance Need Dimension	Growth & Changefulness Dimension
Exhaustion	-0.270**	-0.414**	-0.393**
Cynicism	0.122	-0.200*	0.135
Professional Efficacy	0.440**	0.390**	0.313**

Note. ** $p < 0.01$ * $p < 0.05$

Table 1's findings showed a negative correlation between Task Conferred Dimensions and Exhaustion. It demonstrates how effective organizational health, such as goal concentration, adequate communication, and optional power equalization, reduces employee fatigue. Employee mental weariness can be reduced by assigning tasks. It may lessen employees' feelings of burnout. Because staff turnover is so low-almost nonexistent-employees collaborate better, which contributes to their excellent morale. The results are consistent with (Arnold et al., 2007).

Additionally, there is a negative correlation between the degree of exhaustion and need. Organizational maintenance needs, such as

resource utilization, cohesiveness, and morale, serve to lessen feelings of exhaustion. Employee sensitivity to fatigue may be lessened if the organization's resource use is sufficient. Organizational cohesion and morale also contribute to reducing the susceptibility to fatigue. Similarly, there is a negative correlation between the aspects of growth, changefulness and tiredness. Innovation, independence, and adequate problem-solving are all components of growth and change. Autonomy in government organizations is determined by regulations and the degree to which it must be exercised. As a result, government entities experience the least amount of fatigue. Cynicism has a negative correlation with

exhaustion and maintenance need, two significant aspects of burnout. It is concluded that making effective use of office resources can lessen the perception of working remotely. If workers are drawn to the company, a sense of unity can lessen mistrust. Reducing the sense of distance from work is another benefit of a company with high morale.

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According to the findings, professional efficacy and all three aspects of organizational health are significantly and favourably correlated. It implies that strong organizational health contributes to employees' increased professional efficacy. Employees are more productive in their line of work if the organization's objectives are well-defined and communicated. Professional efficacy is also favourably connected with maintenance requirements such as resource usage, cohesion, and morale. Employee professional efficacy is increased by growth and changeable qualities such as innovativeness, autonomy, and adequate problem resolution. Positive organizational health is found to improve employees' professional efficacy within that organization. These findings are

corroborated by Ghazali et al. (2024) who found an inverse relationship between burnout and organizational health.

Table 2

Significance of Difference for Male and Female for Burnout

Burnout dimensions	Sex	Mean	S.D.	t
Exhaustion	Male	9.05	5.93	3.355**
	Female	5.14	3.07	
Cynicism	Male	29.03	5.21	-1.797*
	Female	30.7	3.25	
Professional Efficacy	Male	7.33	4.34	0.551
	Female	6.72	4.02	

Note. ** $p < 0.01$ * $p < 0.05$

The outcomes of the importance of the difference between organizational health and burnout were shown in Table 2. The findings showed that the variable of exhaustion had a substantial mean difference between males and females. Male employees had higher mean scores than female employees. Compared to women, they are more stressed and tired. Based on presumptions, it may be said that Female workers are more patient compared to male workers. Male and female workers differ significantly in terms of cynicism (at the 0.05 threshold). The average score of female workers is higher than that of male employees. Due to their many responsibilities, Female workers experience greater disengagement from their work.. The outcomes align with (Uppal, 2022). In terms of professional efficacy, there was no appreciable difference between male and female personnel.

Table 3

Significant Inequalities in Workers' Gender for Organizational Health

Dimensions of Organizational Health	Sex	Mean	S.D	t
Task Conferred Dimensions	Male	43.12	7.65	0.759
	Female	41.7	6.42	
Maintenance Need Dimensions	Male	41.24	8.95	-1.120
	Female	43.17	5.11	
Growth and Changefulness Dimensions	Male	54.63	11.76	0.720
	Female	51.74	6.42	

Note. ** $p < 0.01$ * $p < 0.05$

According to Table 3, there was no discernible difference between male and female employees in terms of various organizational health variables, including task conferred dimensions, maintenance need dimensions, and growth and changefulness dimensions. In summary, there is a negative and strong correlation between burnout and organizational health. The average score of female employees is higher than that of male employees. There was no discernible difference between male and female employees in terms of professional efficacy. Growth, Changefulness, Task Conferred Dimensions, and Maintenance Need Dimensions are examples of organizational health. The dimensions of male and female employees vary considerably. This result is similar with the work of (Maclach & Leiter, 1997).

References

Arnold, B., Bakker, A.B., & Evangelia, D.E. (2007). The job demands- resources model:

- state of art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309-328.
- Burke, R.J., & Greenglass, E.R. (2001). Hospital restructuring, work-family conflict and psychological burnout among nursing staff, *Community Work and Family*, 4(1), 49-62.
- Byrne, B.M. (1994). Burnout: testing for the validity, replication, and invariance of causal structure across elementary, intermediate, and secondary teachers. *American Education Research Journal*, 31, 645-673.
- Canadas, G.A., Fuente, D., & Baena, L.R. (2018). Gender, marital status, and children as risk factors for burnout in nurses: A meta-analytic study, *International Journal Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(10), 2102, Pub Med Central.
- Daniel, K.D., Robert, L., & Kahn, R.L. (1978). *The social Psychology of organizations* (2nd ed.) New York: Mc Graw- Hill.
- Ghazali Vardanjani, M., Montazeri, S., Jahanbani Veshare, E., & Ghanbari, S. (2024). Investigating the relationship between organizational health, burnout and job stress among midwives working in hospitals, *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 13, 77.
- Greenglass, E.R., & Burke, R.J. (2001). Hospital restructuring and burnout. *Journal of Health and Human Services Administration*, 25(1), 89-114.
- Handy, J. A. (1988). Theoretical and methodological problems within occupations stress and burnout research, *Human Relations*, 41, 351- 369.

- Haseen, T. (1997). *Organizational health Inventory: Construction and standardization*. Doctoral dissertation, department of Psychology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India.
- Jenkins, S.R., & Maslach, C. (1994). Psychological health and involvement in interpersonally demanding occupations: A longitudinal perspective. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 15, 101-127.
- Kabito, G.G., Wami, S.D., Chercos, & Mekonnen, T.H. (2020). Work related stress and associated factors among academic staffs at the University of Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia: An Institution- based cross sectional study, *Ethiopian Journal of Health Science*, 30(2), 223-232.
- Kobasa, S. C. (1982). Commitment and coping in stress resistance among lawyers. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 42, 707-717.
- Koslowksy, M., Caspy, T., & Lazar, M. (1990). Cause and effect explanations of job satisfaction and commitment: The case of exchange commitment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 125(2), 153-162.
- Lee, R.T., Ashforth, B.E. (1996). A meta-analytic examination of the correlates of the three dimensions of job burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81, 123-133.
- Leiter, M.P. (1993). Burnout as a developmental process: Consideration of models. In W.B. Schaufeli, C. Maslach, and T. Marek (Eds.) *Professional burnout: Recent developments in theory and research* (pp. 237-250). Taylor & Francis.
- Lim, S.Y., & Murphy, L.R. (1999). The relationship of organizational factors to employee health and overall effectiveness. *American Journal of Industrial Medicine Supplement*, 1, 64-65.
- Lowe, G.S., Shannon, H.S., & Schellenberg, G. (2003). Correlates of employees' perceptions of a healthy work environment. *American Journal of Health Promotion*, 17(6), 390-399.
- Marchand, A., Blance, M.E., & Beauregard, N. (2018). Do age and gender contribute to workers' burnout symptoms? *Occupational Medicine*, 68(6), 405-411.
- Maslach, C., & Jackson, S.E. (1981). The measurement of experienced burnout. *Journal of Occupational Behavior*, 2(2), 99-113.
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M.P. (1997). *The truth about burnout: How organizations cause personal stress and what to do about it*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass, 131-150.
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M.P. (2016). Understanding the burnout experience: Recent research its implication for psychiatry. *World Psychiatry*, 15(2), 103-111.
- Maslach, C., Schaufeli, W.B., & Leiter, M.P. (2001). Job burnout, *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, 397-422.
- Mathieu, J. E., & Zajac, D. M. (1990). A review and meta-analysis of the antecedents, correlates, and consequences of organisational commitment. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108, 171-194.
- Miles (1973). Organisational health of training institution. In R.P. Lynton and V. Pareek (Eds.) *V.S. training for development*, Bombay: Taraporewala.
- Ozturk, Y.M. (2020). A theoretical review of burnout syndrome and perspectives of burnout models. *Business Review of Social Sciences*, 2(4), 26-35.
- Purvanova, R.K., & Muros, J.P. (2010). Gender differences in burnout: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 77(2), 168-185.
- Rifin, H.M., & Danaee, M. (2023). Association between Burnout, job dissatisfaction and intention to leave among medical researchers in a research organization in Malaysia during the COVID-19 pandemic, *International Journal of Environment and Research Public Health*, 20(3), 1882.
- Rouseau, D. M. (1995). *Psychological contracts in organizations: Understanding written and unwritten agreements*, 112-130, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Shirom, A. (1989). Burnout in work organizations. In C.L. Cooper and I. Robertson (Eds.), *International review of industrial and organizational psychology* (pp. 25-48). New York: Wiley.
- Uppal, S.K. (2022). Gender difference and relationship of burnout and well-being among employees working from home. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(4), 1156-1166.
- Valsania, S.E., Lagua, A., & Moriano, J.A. (2022). Burnout: A review of theory and measurement, *International Journal of Research public Health*, 19(3), 1780.
- Wilmar, B., Schaufeli, W.B., Arnold, B., & Bakker, A.B. (2000). Burnout contagion processes among teachers, *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 30(11), 2289-2308.
- Wilmar, B., Schaufeli, W.B., Arnold, B., & Bakker, A.B. (2004). Job demands, job resources and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multisample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(3), 293-315.
- Zapf, D., Seifert, C., Schmutte, & Mertini, B.H. (2001). Emotion work and job stressors and their effects on burnout. *Psychology of Health*, 16, 527-545.

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